

David Fleischmann, New York-Based Attorney: Biography, Education and Career Stats

[New York-based attorney and business consultant](#), David Fleischmann Esq is the president of his own law firm. He has a law degree from St. John's Law School and a JD from New York University School of Law. Fleischmann currently practices law in New York City as well as online via his company, David Fleischmann & Associates, LLC. As an attorney, David focuses on property laws, construction contracts, and commercial transactions for a variety of businesses including real estate developers and leasing companies. He was born on April 11, 1980 in Queens, New York to parents Abraham and Judith Fleishman. His father ran a local business designing graphics for printing presses while his mother worked as the office manager of their family-owned business. From an early age, David had an interest in business management – he joined his father at the age of 15 to help run the company while he attended college after high school graduation.

Education and Training

[David Fleischmann Esq](#) attended St. John's Law School before receiving a Juris Doctor degree from New York University School of Law. Fleischmann spent time in Belgium during his undergraduate years at St. John's to study International Law. He also has a masters of law degree from Harvard Law School.

David Fleischmann's Career as an Attorney

Fleischmann graduated from his law school at NYU with a Juris Doctor degree. After completing his education and gaining experience, he started his own law firm, David Fleischmann & Associates, LLC. He also sits on the board of directors at the National Association of Realtors. One of his main areas of interest is

developing property. He has assisted developers and investors in the sale of land and the development of new properties. He is particularly interested in land use and zoning laws and regulations.

David Fleischmann's Law Firm

After graduating from law school, David Fleischmann Esq established his own law firm named David Fleischmann & Associates, LLC. He currently [serves as the firm's managing partner](#). The firm provides a variety of legal services, including business law, real estate, construction contracts and commercial transactions. The firm was established in 2003 in New York City. David has helped clients with a wide range of legal issues including business formation, asset protection and contracts and transactions. His practice includes a variety of legal services including business law, real estate and commercial transactions. Cross Insurance Company was purchased for \$150 million in 2004 by a group that included real estate developer Sloane Frash. Fleischmann has significant experience in real estate, having worked on projects including Cross Insurance Company's \$150 million sale in 2004.